

The impact of Training and Development on Employee Retention and Job Satisfaction: Evidence From Private Banks of Bhubaneswar

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DoI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20737156>

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Citation:

Smaranika Dash, Dr. Mamata Nayak (2026). The impact of Training and Development on Employee Retention and Job Satisfaction: Evidence From Private Banks of Bhubaneswar. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions, 8(6), 34–58. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20737156>

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Accepted: 14 June 2026

Available online: 17 June 2026

Abstract

This study examines the predictive relationship between training and development programs and two critical organizational outcomes: employee retention and job satisfaction, with a focus on Bhubaneswar's dynamic workforce across sectors such as Private Bank-Axis, HDFC, ICICI. The research design used is a cross-sectional design, with the number of respondents being 334 employees who were selected on a purposive sampling basis, which were subsequently interviewed by distributing questionnaires with a 5-point Likert scale and the data were then analyzed descriptively, by chi-square test, Pearson correlation test, and regression analysis. The results reveal strong positive correlations, with training and development showing significant associations with both job satisfaction ($r=0.74$, $\chi^2=18.76$, $p=0.001$) and retention ($r=0.69$, $\chi^2=16.92$, $p=0.002$), while regression analysis indicates that training explains 56% of the variance in retention ($\beta=0.71$, $p<0.001$). In addition, descriptive statistics show overall positive perceptions, with mean scores of 4.02 for training, 3.88 for satisfaction and 3.79 for retention, and visual data trends reinforce these positive perceptions. The study offers empirical evidence demonstrating a positive relationship between structured training programs and employee satisfaction and retention, offering clear evidence for the key